

Jagoan village Boyolali: developing self village through utilizing environmental friendly biogas from cattle wastes

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ABSTRACT

Feces of beef cattles can be utilized as soil amendment and renewable energy. the population of beef cattles in Boyolali regency is raising and their feces potential for materials of biodigester. Biogas energy produced from a fixed dome type digester has been used as the main source of household energy as additional income for farmers. The purpose of the research is to utilize the waste stools of beef cattle farms as biogas to be used for household energy sources, to realize the village's own energy from biogas, the beef cattle farming business in the village takes place without waste and is environmentally friendly. The activity was a part of The Village Partner Development Program which implemented method of : (1) extension using FGD (Focus Group Discussion) technique accompanied by an evaluation of the progress of the level of knowledge and understanding of the material, (2) training in the manufacture and production of household biogas digester production, (3) ongoing monitoring and evaluation. The level of acceptance of biogas technology in Jagoan Village Boyolali was influenced by extension intensity factors, farmer experience, education, motivation and ownership of beef cattle. The farmers' knowledge has increased 120% in producing biogas and 200% in the manufacture of fixed dome type biogas digester installations. Each biogas digester covers 4 family heads. The income of beef cattle business by using biogas in Jagoan Village, Boyolali Regency was obtained from the addition of business revenue with various variables of fixed costs and costs. Scale III income (> 4 head) is greater than scale I (<3 head) and II (3-4 head). LPG gas consumption decreased by 75% and the decrease in fuel wood energy reached 85%. LPG gas savings by 20 tubes per year and 300 bundles of firewood per year.

Keywords: *cattle, biogas, energy, farmers income, environmental Friendly*

INTRODUCTION

Jagoan Village located in Boyolali Regency, Central Java has population density of 100 km² with the number of housed hold 1,086, the total population of 3,768 people, 30% of most of the productive age ranges 25 - 55 years. The condition of Jagoan Village, including livelihoods, is very suitable for beef cattle farming. Livestock groups "Sambi Mulyo", "Berkah Mulyo" and "Sido Mulyo" in

Jagoan Village, Sambu District, Boyolali Regency are groups of fattening livestock. The most breedings of beef cattle are Simmental ongole crossbred and Limousin ongole crossbreed cattle business. The existence of this group as a media of togetherness expand the fattening of cattle in Jagoan Village, the economic zone and the welfare of families and communities.

One of beef cattle breeding business is feces waste or manure. However feces waste has not been upgraded economically. The farmer groups at Jagoan village have 100 – 175 livestock that managed by 60 farmers and each farmer has 2-3 cows. The member of farmer group is 150 people. Cattle fattened for 4-5 months. Each cow produces fresh manure range of 15-30 kg per day which can 2 m³ of biogas or equivalent to LPG 9.6 kg (Lutojo et al., 2014a).

Biogas can save costs of IDR 200,000 per month for cooking purposes compared to LPG (Lutojo et al., 2014b). The produced biogas is distributed through pipes with a radius of up to 1 km from the cattle cage to housing for cooking purposes (Lutojo et al., 2010). However, only 10% of Jagoan villagers whom install biodigester as a source of stove energy, while 90% do not utilize feces as a source of biogas energy. Efforts are needed to increase the existing biogas capacity with socializing the manufacture of a new biogas digester for all farmers to realize an energy independent village.

The general objective of the Program of Self-Village Development under the Ministry of Research and Technology in 2017 - 2019 is to realize the Jagoan Village, Boyolali district as the independent village of biogas bioenergy and the welfare of community. The special objective is Jagoan Village to become a village with communities and breeders who rely on household energy using biogas energy and save on LPG energy usage costs. The following program impact is that beef cattle farming in Jagoan Village, Boyolali takes place environmentally friendly and zero waste. The purpose of the research is to utilize the waste stools of beef cattle farms as biogas to be used for household energy sources, to realize the village's own energy from biogas, the beef cattle farming business in the village takes place without waste and is environmentally friendly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Science and Technology Application Method

Instructional methods and dialogues through extension program activities using FGD (Focus Group Discussion) techniques were accompanied by an evaluation of the progress of the level of knowledge and understanding of the material by calculating the percentage of progress in the form of a comparison of the pre-test and post-test values. Material consisted of the understanding of biogas, biogas processes, benefits of biogas, biogas installation

components, biogas digester manufacturing, biogas production methods, biogas stove handling and biogas treatment. Training method was done through demonstration of making biogas digester method by making and applying biogas digester.

Extension activities with the FGD method were carried out to transfer science and technology from the team to the target group to solve the problems being faced, which were related to the management of biogas production management (Lutojo and Riyanto, 2014). Counseling was carried out through lecture and discussion methods. To find out the acceptance and increase knowledge and understanding of faecal potential, pre-test and post-test evaluations were carried out (Lutojo et al., 2010). The pre-test and post-test material was made the same time, the pre-test was carried out before extension and post-test was carried out after counseling. Evaluation material was related to faecal utilization for biogas production. The evaluation was made by inviting farmer to answer 15 questions. Each question only provides two answers, correct or wrong. Participants choose answers by crossing the answer sheet. Evaluation of the level of progress was calculated by looking for the percentage of correct answers from 15 questions both pre-test and post-test, then the difference in value is sought by the percentage of the pre-test value. The application and socialization of making biogas digester followed Lutojo et al. (2010). The use of monitoring methods through integrated and continuous monitoring techniques involves linkages between agricultural agency in Boyolali and local government with the IbDM Team of the Animal Husbandry Department of UNS carried out FGD techniques which accompanied by an evaluation of the progress of the level of knowledge and understanding of material in various activities such as dissemination of information programs, demonstration plots, marketing, monitoring and evaluation, reporting, presentation of results of activities, publications in journals.

Linkage Model

The PPDM involves the Animal Husbandry Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Sebelas Maret University, with the, the local government of Boyolali District, Central Java Province, and the Livestock Group "Sambi Mulyo", "Berkah Mulyo" and "Sido Mulyo" Boyolali. The Role of IbDM Team Animal Husbandry Department Faculty of Agriculture Sebelas Maret University is as an innovation carrier in the form of socialization of the manufacture of biogas digester.

Evaluate the results of activities

Evaluation of activity results was carried out thoroughly and continuously by giving an assessment of the farmer's response to counseling about the use of household-scale biogas installations. Evaluated results of training and skills of farmers are focused on the implementation of household-scale biogas digester. The level of new income additions for beef cattle farmers "Sambi Mulyo", "Berkah Mulyo" and "Sido Mulyo" Boyolali was also evaluated, including who use biogas as the main energy source for household scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Counseling and Training

Counseling is done to transfer science and technology from the team to the target group to solve the problem being faced, which is related to the management of biogas production. The problem of potential use of faeces as biogas materials and the knowledge of farmers who have not been able to maximize faeces are resolved through counseling and training. The faeces or cow dung in Jagoan village presently still are as waste and do not maximally utilized their economic value.

Farmers' knowledge on faecal utilization is still limited to being a source of organic fertilizer only and most of the feces are still disposed of around the cage. Manure is an organic material that stores farmers' knowledge of faecal utilization, which is still disposed of around the cage. Manure is an organic material that holds potentially as energy source in the form of biogas which can be used as a source of energy for stoves for households. The purpose of the extension activities is to provide knowledge and understanding of the use of biogas from fecal beef cattle for energy biogas stoves. Potential of biogas as an energy source can be used for home stoves stairs. The value of material knowledge progress was 120% for Sambi Mulyo, 165% for Sido Mulyo, and 105% for Berkah Mulyo. The role of farmers in a participatory manner and extension workers must be synergized well, so that the impact of counseling itself can be seen to the fullest.

Pilot Project

The 10 m³ biogas installation was made to accommodate for 4-5 head of beef cattle. The cage renovation is needed to make the stool flow perfectly into the biogas installation. A biogas installation is made with a fixed dome model or a model of a digester dome remains permanently planted in the ground. The biogas installation includes the inlet, digester, outlet, and container of biogas waste (slurry). The completeness of the biogas installation is included in this

activity, namely the installation of a biogas purification unit, installation of a paralon to transport biogas to the farmer's stove, and the procurement of a biogas stove.

It has been built and started producing biogas from the installation. Biogas from biogas stoves can already be used as a household energy source. Currently farmers who use biogas stoves are no longer using household energy sources from LPG. Within one month the farmer can save cost of purchasing 2 LPG tubes worth IDR 30,000 per month. Each unit of biogas capacity of 10m³ biogas is flowed from the digester unit to the paralon pipe to the farmer's house. The distance between the biogas installation and the breeder's house is the closest to 10 meters and the farthest 300 m. Management of the handling and use of biogas is regulated by farmers by alternately channeling feces into the stirring unit, mixing feces with water, and stirring. Every day the collected stool is channeled to the stirring unit before entering the digester. Stirring is done every morning alternately. Biogas stoves by farmers are used as a heat source for cooking, boiling water and others.

Results Evaluation

In Jagoan Village, the use of feces for biodigester has been carried out. The faeces are currently increasing in value, which previously was only as waste, now increase its value to become a source of biogas. Stored beef cattle there are no more stools. Cages become cleaner and healthier and there is no waste anymore (zero waste) and the environment becomes healthy and environment friendly. Farmers have increased their understanding of the demand for faecal use for biogas production. For farmers whose houses are not adjacent to the cage, biogas is flowed using plastic paralon pipes from the biogas installation to the house. Since using biogas stoves, farmers have never used LPG again for household energy. The cage building and environment are healthy and easy to clean and there are no more stools around the cage.

Factors for receiving biogas technology.

The extension intensity factor and the farmer experience influence the acceptance of biogas technology, while the education, motivation and beef cattle ownership factors do not affect the acceptance of biogas technology in livestock farmer groups in Jagoan Village. Acceptance of biogas technology is influenced by two factors, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors influence acceptance of age biogas, formal education, non-formal education, income, livestock ownership, cosmopolitan level and farmer experience, while external factors influence biogas revenues are extension agents, institutional support and external motivation. These factors will be maximized if all elements

consciously and responsibly accept the biogas technology (Lukman, 2008). At the farmer level, the extension activities are directed on farmers behavior in accepting a technology. However, most farmers decided to reject the technology, even though has been tested on other farmers but there is difficulty to change the farmer's belief in receiving a biogas technology (Novikarumsari, 2014).

Business contributions and income

The income of beef cattle business by using biogas in Jagoan Village, Boyolali Regency is obtained from the sum of business income of beef cattle by using biogas which is reduced by the amount of fixed costs and variable costs. The results showed that scale III was bigger than scale I (<3 head) and II (3-4 head). This is influenced by the sale of more cattle. Scale III (> 4 head) of beef cattle business with biogas utilization has higher income. According to Hernanto (1993), the greater productivity or number of products produced will be higher income derived from the business.

The contribution of beef cattle business to use livestock manure into biodigester on farmer income is the percentage of income derived from beef cattle folk business by using biogas on the total income of beef cattle farmers. The source of income of beef cattle farmers comes from beef cattle business by using biogas and other businesses. According to Rubiansyah (2001), the greater income from outside the livestock business obtained by the farmer will be more cash so that the capital to develop the business is greater. The contribution of income derived from beef cattle business by using livestock manure into biogas is diverse. Sohadji (1992) states that scale II is still classified as a part-time business because income is still below 30%, on a scale I and III can be said that the business becomes a major or commercial business. According to Rubiansyah (2001), the income contribution of a business is small (<30%) then the business is a part-time business.

The income of biogas farmers is higher than the income of non-biogas farmers. There is a difference between the income of biogas farmers and non-biogas farmers. Energy consumption by farmers changes after using biogas. Energy consumption decreased 3 times from before. The existence of biogas affects the level of energy consumption by farmers in saving energy derived from LPG and firewood. The decrease of the two energy sources is more than double the initial use. LPG gas consumption decreased by 75% and decreased fuel wood energy consumption reached 85%. LPG gas is saved by 20 tubes per year and 300 bundles of firewood per year. The amount of energy used by respondents to cook both from LPG and fuel wood also changes before and after using biogas. The biogas technology used by farmers gives economical benefits,

namely decreased LPG and fuel wood energy consumption after using biogas. According to Elizabeth and Rusdiana (2011), biogas technology is the proper utilization of beef cattle waste to produce energy as well as organic fertilizer. This means that biogas gives environmental and economical benefits.

CONCLUSIONS

The acceptance level of biogas technology in Jagoan Village Boyolali is influenced by extension intensity factors, farmer experience, education, motivation and ownership of beef cattle. Farmers' knowledge has increased 120% in producing biogas and 200% in the manufacture of fixed dome type biogas digester installations. With using biogas, the environment is healthy, safe, no stool odor, and environmentally friendly. Biogas is used as a household energy source that to meet the daily needs of the family. There has been a decline in LPG use by 70% and a decrease in the use of firewood 55%.

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